

RehabMove 2018: PERIOD PREVALENCE AND POINT PREVALENCE OF SPORTS-RELATED INJURIES AND ILLNESSES IN SWEDISH PARALYMPIC ATHLETES

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PURPOSE: To describe among Paralympic athletes the 1-year retrospective period prevalence of severe sports-related injuries and illnesses (SRIIPS) and point prevalence of SRIIPS, and to examine possible differences in prevalence proportions of SRIIPS, between athletes with different demographics, and characteristics related to their behavior, impairment, pain and sport.

METHODS: A total of 104 Paralympic athletes responded to a questionnaire with questions about period prevalence of severe SRIIPS, point prevalence of SRIIPS, and athlete characteristics. Differences in prevalence proportions were analysed with chi-square statistics.

RESULTS: In summary, 31% (95% CI 23-40) reported a severe injury, 32% (95% CI 24-41) a current injury, 14% (95% CI 9-23) reported a severe illness and 14% (95% CI 8-22) a current illness. More severe injuries ($p < .05$) were reported by athletes that were 18-25 years, not using an assistive device, having pain during training, using analgesics, continuing training when injured and feeling guilt when missing exercise. Athletes that reported a previous severe injury, having pain in daily life and during training, using NSAID and being upset when unable to exercise, had higher point prevalence of injuries ($p < .05$). Athletes below age 30 years reported more severe illnesses ($p < .05$). Being female, previous severe illness, using prescribed medications and feeling anxious/depressed were associated with more present illnesses ($p < .05$).

CONCLUSIONS: Paralympic athletes, in particular of younger age, reported a fairly high prevalence of SRIIPS. Also, mental aspects as well as pain and use of medication seem to play a role in the occurrence of SRIIPS. This indicates that the existence of associated factors for SRIIPS is complex and calls for a broad biopsychosocial approach when developing preventive measures. Further large prospective studies are needed to identify risk factors and causations to provide stronger evidence for prevention.